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Protonation Reaction Between Cobalt Phosphate and Urea Nitrate in the Solid State

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AFTER the establishment of the essentiality of cobalt for leguminous plants and nitrogen fixing bacteria¹, a lot of work has been done about the influence of micronutrients upon the availability of macronutrients to plants under different soil conditions. Cobalt and iron have similar ionic radii, charges, can replace each other and occur together in many geological materials. Acid soils containing iron phosphates is unavailable to plants because it can convert "available" phosphate to "unavailable" phosphate². To make iron or cobalt

phosphate available to plants especially in acid soils is therefore of considerable interest in soil chemistry. In the present investigation an attempt has therefore been made to study the protonation reaction between tribasic cobalt phosphate and urea nitrate on the lines reported by one of the authors in an earlier communication³, so as to ascertain the possibility of using urea nitrate for releasing phosphates of acidic soils containing iron or cobalt phosphate.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were BDH AnalaR grade. A series of mixtures were prepared by mixing 1 mole of $\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$ with varying amounts of urea nitrate and each mixture was ground in an agate mortar for about an hour under dry conditions. The extent of availability of phosphate in the ground mixture was determined by methods reported earlier⁴.

Results and Discussion

The results indicate that the water solubility and citrate solubility (Table 1) of the phosphate in the various products obtained on grinding tricobalt phos-

TABLE 1—WATER AND CITRATE SOLUBLE P_2O_5 IN COBALT PHOSPHATE—UREA NITRATE MIXTURE

Cobalt phosphate to urea nitrate mole ratio	Total P_2O_5 %	Water soluble P_2O_5 %	Citrate soluble P_2O_5 %	Fraction of water soluble P_2O_5 %	Fraction of citrate soluble P_2O_5 %
1:0	38.71				
1:1	28.99	3.17	12.95	10.96	44.70
1:1.50	25.75	3.19	16.58	12.42	64.38
1:2.00	23.17	4.90	16.44	21.18	70.96
1:2.50	21.05	10.51	9.77	49.92	46.44
1:3.00	19.29	12.42	6.58	64.38	34.11
1:3.25	18.52	14.41	3.75	77.79	20.28
1:3.50	17.81	17.36	0.24	97.50	1.36
1:3.75	17.14	17.06	—	99.52	—
1:4.00	16.53	16.51	—	99.86	—

phate with increasing amount of urea nitrate gradually increases and decreases respectively. At the stage of 1 : 4 mole ratio cent per cent water soluble mixture is obtained.

The interaction occurs in two steps

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Like an earlier work (3) this conclusion is drawn for the following reasons :

(A) No alcohol soluble phosphate is detected in the ground mixture of urea nitrate and cobalt phosphate.

(B) The results (Table 2) indicate that cobalt nitrate formed in the reaction increases with the increasing amount of urea nitrate and reaches a limiting value when the mole ratio of cobalt phosphate to urea nitrate is 1 : 2.

TABLE 2—COBALT NITRATE CONTENT IN ETHANOL EXTRACT
[Cobalt phosphate, 7.3358 g + urea nitrate]

Weight of urea nitrate (g)	Cobalt phosphate to urea nitrate mole ratio	Cobalt nitrate Found (g)	Cobalt nitrate Calculated (g)
1.23	1:0.50	0.2464	0.9146
2.46	1:1.00	1.4946	1.8293
3.69	1:1.50	2.5212	2.7439
4.92	1:2.00	3.3709	3.6585
6.15	1:2.50	3.3710	3.6585

(C) At the later stage of grinding the mixture forms a paste.

This investigation indicates that unavailable phosphatic minerals of iron or cobalt in acidic soils may be made available to plants by using urea nitrate.

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Studies on the Conditions of Formations of Heteropoly Decavanadocobaltates

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THE existence of $[\text{V}_{10}\text{O}_{28}]^{6-}$ polyanion, depending upon vanadium ion concentration and pH has been reported¹ and the crystal structures of a few heteropoly complexes of this isopoly anion with Ca and Zn

as the heteroatom, have been elucidated². Chemical literature does not reveal any exhaustive studies on the formation of vanadocobaltate heteropoly complexes. The present communication deals with the conditions of formation and apparent molecular weight determinations of new heteropoly complexes: $(\text{NH}_4)_4 [\text{CoV}_{10}\text{O}_{28}] 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{H}_2 [\text{H}_2\text{V}_{10}\text{O}_{28}] 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$. These two heteropoly compounds, one being ammonium salt and the other being its free acid, have been formed with different concentrations of the reacting substances and at different pH.

Ammonium 10 Heteropolyvanadocobaltate (II) :

Solutions of arbitrary concentrations of the reactants, when mixed together, may cause immediate precipitation, leading to the formation of a compound with indefinite composition. When solution of .004 M cobaltous chloride and .05 M ammonium metavanadate were mixed together with 20 ml of glacial acetic acid, they did not give rise to immediate precipitation. So, 50 ml. of .05 M ammonium metavanadate mixed with 20 ml. of glacial acetic acid was gradually added by one ml. in each turn to 50 ml. of .004 M cobaltous chloride solution and an extensive study on the pH variation of the system was carried out as discussed in the previous detailed communications³. There was a gradual decrease in the pH of the solution up to the addition of 45 ml. of ammonium metavanadate and glacial acetic acid mixture. It was then followed by a plateau of constant pH of 4.5 up to 54 ml. of ammonium metavanadate reactant mixture. Thermometric titrations⁴ corroborated the above results. By comparing these two curves⁵ the range in volume of the reactants could be studied. So, 54 ml. of .05 M ammonium metavanadate - glacial acetic acid mixture was added to 50 ml. of .004 M cobaltous chloride solution with constant vigorous stirring and refluxed for one and half hour in a round bottom flask, evaporated to crystallisation and left in vacuum. After nine days interval of time light orange shining crystals were isolated from the mother liquor and were recrystallised from lukewarm water. The complete analysis of the compound was done by chemical and instrumental methods. Vanadium was estimated colorimetrically by hydrogen peroxide method⁶. Cobalt was estimated gravimetrically⁷ weighing as CoSO_4 at 450-500. Nitrogen and hydrogen were estimated by element estimation technique. (Found: Co, 3.98; V, 36; N, 3.85; H, 3.69; calcd. for $(\text{NH}_4)_4 [\text{CoV}_{10}\text{O}_{28}] 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Co, 4.16; V, 36.09; N, 3.96; H, 3.68%), as suggested by Evans for complex heteropoly anion $[\text{X}^n \text{V}_{10}\text{O}_{28}]^{(6-n)-}$.

10-Heteropolyvanadocobaltous (II) Acid :

In this case 50 ml. of .1M ammonium metavanadate mixed with 25 ml. of glacial acetic acid was gradually added to 50 ml. of .006 M cobaltous chloride solution and pH and thermometric studies of the system were done separately as discussed for the previous compound. By comparing the graphs the volume of the reactants, at which the constant pH 3.7 was maintained, was